

Multi-Sensor UAV Validation of Sentinel-2 NDVI as an Operational Tool for Environmental Monitoring and Situational Awareness in a Heterogeneous Riparian System (Fusaro Lake, Italy)

Mohammed Ajaoud¹, Muhammad Zaid Qamar¹, Cristiano Ciccarelli¹, Massimiliano Lega^{1,*}

¹ Department of Engineering, University of Napoli 'Parthenope', Centro Direzionale, Isola C4, 80143 Napoli, NA, Italy, mohammed.ajaoud001@studenti.uniparthenope.it, muhammadzaid.qamar001@studenti.uniparthenope.it, cristiano.ciccarelli001@studenti.uniparthenope.it, massimiliano.lega@uniparthenope.it

* corresponding author

doi: 10.5281/zenodo.20396237

Abstract: UAV imagery resolves fine-scale vegetation structure that satellite sensors cannot; satellites provide the spatial coverage that UAVs lack. Reconciling observations across these scales requires cross-resolution validation and rigorous uncertainty quantification. This study fused UAV multispectral and thermal data with Sentinel-2 imagery to characterize vegetation patterns around Fusaro Lake, Naples, Italy. The UAV NDVI orthomosaic was resampled to Sentinel-2 resolution for direct comparison, and a pixel-level error map was produced to spatialize residual discrepancies. Results indicated strong agreement ($r = 0.885$, $R^2 = 0.73$), alongside a positive bias (MBE = +0.102) attributable to mixed-pixel dilution at sub-pixel land-cover transitions. An RMSE of 0.296 confirms that random variability from spectral response differences and atmospheric correction residuals dominates over systematic error. Vegetation edges registered 43.4% high-error pixels compared to 28.1% in spectrally homogeneous zones, a 1.4× amplification attributable to mixed-pixel effects. Thermal data identified a 4–5 °C land–water gradient spatially coincident with peak NDVI discrepancies, establishing ecotonal heterogeneity as the primary driver of cross-scale observation uncertainty. This multi-sensor approach quantifies satellite uncertainties and enhances situational awareness, providing a transferable framework for sanitary-environmental engineering in complex ecosystems.

Keywords: environmental monitoring; UAV multispectral and thermal; satellite; NDVI.

1 Introduction

Remote sensing is now a standard tool for environmental monitoring rather than a specialist one. Sentinel-2 delivers multispectral coverage at 10–60 m resolution suited to regional vegetation assessment (Drusch et al. 2012), and its derived NDVI is widely used as a proxy for vegetation condition (Tucker 1979, Rouse 1973). Yet Sentinel-2 NDVI uncertainty varies across space and time (De Petris et al. 2023), and mixed-pixel effects introduce substantial error in heterogeneous landscapes (Cracknell 1998). UAVs occupy the observational gap between ground surveys and satellite overpasses, supporting high-resolution environmental characterization at local scales (Tmušić et al. 2020, Maes and Steppe 2019, Ajaoud et al. 2025). Their tendency to systematically overestimate NDVI relative to satellite sensors (Isaev et al. 2023) is documented but poorly understood in natural ecosystems. Riparian and coastal lagoon environments are especially difficult to

characterize because sharp land–water transitions amplify mixed-pixel contamination (Cracknell 1998). This study validates Sentinel-2 NDVI against UAV multispectral observations at Fusaro Lake, a protected coastal lagoon northwest of Naples, Italy. Spatial discrepancies between platforms are mapped at pixel level, and their relationship with thermal gradients at the land–water interface is examined. Cross-platform differences are treated not as noise to be minimized but as spatial indicators of environmental heterogeneity, with direct relevance to sanitary-environmental engineering applications. The novelty of the present study lies in three aspects: First, cross-platform NDVI uncertainty is spatialised as an indicator of environmental heterogeneity rather than treated as error to be minimised. Second, UAV thermal imagery is introduced as an independent, spectrally orthogonal diagnostic layer that physically explains the spatial distribution of NDVI discrepancies. Third, the framework is demonstrated in a sanitary-environmental engineering context at a protected coastal lagoon, where operational monitoring decisions depend directly on the reliability of vegetation indices. Taken together, these contributions move multi-sensor UAV data beyond simple validation toward active uncertainty mapping for environmental management.

2 Materials and methods

2.1 Study area

Fusaro Lake (40°49'N, 14°03'E) is a shallow coastal lagoon in the Campi Flegrei district, roughly 20 km northwest of Naples, Italy (Figure 1). It covers approximately 1.2 km² and

Figure 1. Geographic location of Lake Fusaro.

maintains a direct connection to the Tyrrhenian Sea. The site is characterised by abrupt transitions between open water, emergent vegetation, bare soil, and built surfaces conditions that make it well suited for cross-platform NDVI validation.

2.2 Data acquisition and processing

The UAV survey was conducted on 16 May 2024 using two DJI Mavic series platforms. The Mavic 3T carried a thermal sensor based on an uncooled VOx microbolometer operating in the long-wave infrared range. The Mavic 3 Multispectral integrated a 20 MP RGB camera alongside four narrowband sensors covering green, red, red-edge, and near-infrared wavelengths. Both platforms flew with RTK positioning referenced to a D-RTK 2 GNSS base station, achieving centimetre-level geolocation accuracy. Flight plans used 80% front overlap and 75% side overlap to ensure robust photogrammetric reconstruction. Multispectral imagery was processed in Pix4Dfields (v2.12.0) to produce an NDVI orthomosaic using the standard band-ratio formulation.

$$NDVI = \frac{NIR - Red}{NIR + Red} \quad (1)$$

Thermal imagery was processed in Agisoft Metashape (v2.02) to produce a georeferenced land surface temperature orthomosaic.

A Sentinel-2 Level-2A surface reflectance image for the same date (16 May 2024) was obtained from the Copernicus Open Access Hub, keeping acquisition conditions consistent across platforms. Sentinel-2 NDVI was derived from Band 4 (Red, 665 nm) and Band 8 (NIR, 842 nm) at 10 m spatial resolution, with atmospheric correction applied via the Sen2Cor algorithm.

2.3 Cross-platform NDVI comparison

The UAV NDVI orthomosaic was spatially aggregated to 10 m using mean resampling, whereby each output pixel represents the arithmetic mean of all valid UAV sub-pixels within the corresponding Sentinel-2 footprint. The resampled raster was co-registered to the Sentinel-2 grid before any comparison to ensure precise spatial alignment. Pixels with missing data in either layer were excluded, along with cloud- and shadow-affected pixels flagged by the Scene Classification Layer (SCL). Cross-platform agreement was quantified via Pearson correlation

(r), coefficient of determination (R^2), mean bias error (MBE), and root mean square error (RMSE), with linear regression performed using Sentinel-2 NDVI as the dependent variable and aggregated UAV NDVI as the independent variable. All analyses were implemented in Python 3.10.

2.4 NDVI error mapping and edge analysis

The NDVI error map was computed as the pixel-wise signed difference between aggregated UAV NDVI and Sentinel-2 NDVI ($UAV - S2$), yielding a continuous error surface bounded between -1 and $+1$. Absolute error was then grouped into three classes: low ($|\Delta NDVI| \leq 0.1$), moderate ($0.1 < |\Delta NDVI| \leq 0.2$), and high ($|\Delta NDVI| > 0.2$). Vegetation edges were delineated by applying a Sobel edge-detection filter to the UAV NDVI orthomosaic and thresholding the resulting gradient magnitude to produce a binary edge mask. High-error pixel proportions were calculated separately for edge and non-edge zones to isolate the contribution of mixed-pixel effects to cross-platform discrepancy.

2.5 Thermal analysis

Thermal imagery from the UAV was used to examine surface temperature conditions at the land-water interface. Profiles were extracted along transects oriented perpendicular to representative shoreline segments. The temperature gradient (ΔT) was defined as the difference between mean surface temperature over vegetated land pixels and open water pixels.

3 Results

3.1 UAV NDVI orthomosaic and Sentinel-2 NDVI

Figure 2 presents the UAV RGB orthomosaic (a), high-resolution UAV multispectral NDVI (b), aggregated UAV NDVI at 10 m resolution (c), and Sentinel-2 NDVI (d). The full-resolution UAV NDVI resolves fine-scale vegetation variability that smooths out after aggregation, though the main spatial patterns are retained. Sentinel-2 reproduces the broad vegetation distribution but loses the within-pixel heterogeneity visible in the UAV data.

Figure 2. NDVI comparison at Fusaro Lake: (a) RGB orthomosaic, (b) UAV NDVI, (c) aggregated UAV NDVI at 10 m, and (d) Sentinel-2 NDVI at 10 m.

3.2 Cross-platform statistical agreement

Comparison between aggregated UAV NDVI and Sentinel-2 NDVI gave a Pearson correlation of $r = 0.885$ ($p < 0.001$) and $R^2 = 0.73$. UAV NDVI was consistently higher than Sentinel-2, producing a positive mean bias error (MBE = +0.102). RMSE reached 0.296, nearly three times the MBE. Linear regression returned $S2_NDVI = 0.82 \times UAV_NDVI + 0.06$, with a sub-unity slope and positive intercept. Co-registration assessment yielded a final RMSE of 0.91 m, confirming sub-pixel geometric alignment between platforms (Figure 3).

Figure 3. Scatterplot of Sentinel-2 NDVI versus aggregated UAV NDVI.

3.3 Error map and edge analysis

The NDVI error map (UAV – Sentinel-2) showed spatially structured rather than random discrepancies across the study area (Figure 4). Most pixels carried small differences, though pronounced deviations emerged along vegetation boundaries. A positive error band was consistently present along the shoreline. Low-error pixels ($|\Delta NDVI| \leq 0.1$) dominated the classification, with moderate and high errors concentrated at vegetation edges. Vegetation edge

Figure 4. NDVI error analysis: (a) signed error map (UAV – Sentinel-2), (b) absolute error classification, and (c) high error rate by zone.

pixels exhibited 43.4% high error rates compared to 28.1% in homogeneous areas, yielding a 1.4× amplification factor.

3.4 Thermal imagery and ecotonal analysis

The UAV thermal orthomosaic resolved a 4–5 °C surface temperature gradient at the land–water interface of Fusaro Lake (Figure 5), forming a distinct transition zone along the shoreline. This zone corresponded spatially with the areas of greatest NDVI discrepancy between UAV and Sentinel-2.

Figure 5. UAV thermal map of Fusaro Lake showing the land surface temperature gradient ($\Delta T \approx 4\text{--}5^\circ\text{C}$) at the land–water interface.

4 Discussion

The strong correlation between aggregated UAV and Sentinel-2 NDVI ($r = 0.885$, $R^2 = 0.73$) confirms that Sentinel-2 reliably captures dominant vegetation patterns at Fusaro Lake, in line with multi-platform validation studies across diverse ecosystems (Tmušić et al. 2020, Maes and Steppe 2019). The positive bias (MBE = +0.102, UAV – Sentinel-2) indicates that Sentinel-2 slightly underestimates NDVI relative to UAV and is attributable to the mixed-pixel effect: Sentinel-2 pixels integrate spectral contributions from multiple land-cover types, attenuating the pure vegetation signal (Cracknell 1998). Comparable UAV-to-satellite overestimation has been documented in heterogeneous montane landscapes (Isaev et al. 2023). The regression slope of 0.82 supports this mechanism dilution intensifies at higher vegetation densities, where the spectral contrast between vegetated and non-vegetated sub-pixel fractions is greatest.

The RMSE of 0.296, nearly three times the MBE, indicates that random error dominates the overall discrepancy. Likely sources include spectral response function differences between sensors, residual atmospheric correction artifacts, and sub-pixel co-registration imprecision. De Petris et al. 2023 showed that Sentinel-2 NDVI carries inherent measurement uncertainty independent of landscape heterogeneity, consistent with the baseline error observed here even within homogeneous zones. The 1.4× amplification of high-error rates at vegetation edges directly quantifies the mixed-pixel effect and is consistent with established mixed-pixel theory (Cracknell 1998). Li et al. 2023 reported comparable boundary-driven amplification in urban environments, suggesting this pattern is a general feature of moderate-resolution satellite observations. The residual 28.1% high-error rate within homogeneous zones confirms that sensor- and processing-level factors contribute meaningful uncertainty even where land cover is spectrally uniform. The 4–5 °C thermal gradient at the land–water interface falls spatially on the areas of greatest NDVI discrepancy, in line with riparian thermal studies (Alphonse et al. 2024, Casas-Mulet et al. 2020). This correspondence supports the interpretation that abrupt surface property transitions within a single satellite pixel footprint generate the strongest spectral mixing effects. Thermal imagery consequently offers an independent means of locating where satellite vegetation indices are least reliable. Several limitations apply. The analysis covers a single acquisition date, so temporal variability in the error structure cannot be assessed. Only one site was examined, and whether the observed amplification factors hold for other coastal lagoon systems remains to be tested. It should be acknowledged that UAV-derived NDVI is not an absolute radiometric reference. UAV sensors carry known limitations: spectral response functions that differ from satellite bands, vignetting across the field of view, and residual atmospheric path contributions even at low operating altitudes. UAV NDVI is therefore treated here as a high-resolution spatial proxy rather than ground truth, a position justified by its centimetre-scale resolution relative to the 10 m Sentinel-2 pixel, which substantially reduces

mixed-pixel contributions. Sentinel-2 NDVI performs well for regional vegetation assessment but loses reliability in ecotonal zones. Combining UAV multispectral and thermal data with satellite imagery offers a practical method for spatialising observation uncertainty in structurally complex coastal ecosystems.

5 Conclusions

Combining UAV multispectral and thermal data with Sentinel-2 imagery produces a workable framework for monitoring heterogeneous riparian ecosystems. Sentinel-2 reproduces broad vegetation patterns reliably, but accuracy degrades at ecotonal boundaries where mixed-pixel effects dominate. Thermal data independently links peak NDVI discrepancies to sharp surface temperature gradients at the land–water interface, converting cross-platform uncertainty into spatial indicators of environmental heterogeneity with direct relevance to sanitary-environmental engineering. For operational use of Sentinel-2 in heterogeneous landscapes, the NDVI error map developed here can function as a decision-support layer. Homogeneous vegetation zones carry acceptable uncertainty and can be monitored with confidence, while edge pixels and land–water ecotones warrant cautious interpretation or supplementation with higher-resolution data. Multi-temporal analysis and super-resolution techniques are natural extensions of this approach.

Acknowledgments: This work was supported by the UNESCO Chair "Environment, Resources and Sustainable Development," the Italian Aerospace Research Centre (CIRA), and Prof. Lega's SaFe team.

6 References

- Ajaoud, M., Ciccarelli, C., De Mizio, M., Gargiulo, M., Parrilli, S., Savarese, C., Tufano, F., Lega, M., 2025. Bridging sustainability and environmental impact assessment: multi-scale bioindication and remote sensing for pollution monitoring in agroecosystems. *Sustainability* 17 (9), 4115.
- Alphonse, A.B., Osuch, M., Wawrzyniak, T., Hanselmann, N., 2024. Spatio-temporal variability of surface temperatures in High Arctic periglacial environment using UAV thermal imagery and in-situ measurements. *GIScience & Remote Sensing* 61 (1), 2435851.
- Casas-Mulet, R., Pander, J., Ryu, D., Stewardson, M.J., Geist, J., 2020. Unmanned aerial vehicle (UAV)-based thermal infra-red (TIR) and optical imagery reveals multi-spatial scale controls of cold-water areas over a groundwater-dominated riverscape. *Frontiers in Environmental Science* 8, 64.
- Cracknell, A.P., 1998. Review article: Synergy in remote sensing—what's in a pixel? *International Journal of Remote Sensing* 19 (11), 2025–2047.
- De Petris, S., Sarvia, F., Borgogno-Mondino, E., 2023. Uncertainty assessment of Sentinel-2-retrieved vegetation spectral indices over Europe. *European Journal of Remote Sensing* 56(1), 2267169.
- Drusch, M., Del Bello, U., Carlier, S., Colin, O., Fernandez, V., Gascon, F., Hoersch, B., Isola, C., Laberinti, P., Martimort,

- P., Meygret, A., Spoto, F., Sy, O., Marchese, F., Bargellini, P., 2012. Sentinel-2: ESA's optical high-resolution mission for GMES operational services. *Remote Sensing of Environment* 120, 25–36.
- Isaev, E., Kulikov, M., Shibkov, E., Sidle, R.C., 2023. Bias correction of Sentinel-2 with unmanned aerial vehicle multispectral data for use in monitoring walnut fruit forest in western Tien Shan, Kyrgyzstan. *Journal of Applied Remote Sensing* 17 (2), 022204.
- Li, S., Zhou, Z., Ma, R., Liu, S., Guan, Q., 2023. Extracting subpixel vegetation NDVI time series for evaluating the mixed pixel effect on GPP estimation in urban areas. *International Journal of Digital Earth* 16 (1), 3222–3238.
- Maes, W.H., Steppe, K., 2019. Perspectives for remote sensing with unmanned aerial vehicles in precision agriculture. *Trends in Plant Science* 24 (2), 152–164.
- Rouse, W., 1973. Monitoring vegetation system in the Great Plains with ERTS. *Proc. 3rd ERTS Symposium, NASA, Washington, DC, Vol. 1, pp. 309–317.*
- Tmušić, G., Manfreda, S., Aasen, H., James, M.R., Gonçalves, G., Ben-Dor, E., Brook, A., Polinova, M., Arranz, J.J., Mészáros, J., Zhuang, R., Johansen, K., Malbeteau, Y., Pedroso de Lima, I., Davids, C., Herban, S., McCabe, M.F., 2020. Current practices in UAS-based environmental monitoring. *Remote Sensing* 12 (6), 1001.
- Tucker, C.J., 1979. Red and photographic infrared linear combinations for monitoring vegetation. *Remote Sensing of Environment* 8 (2), 127–150.